

MOU with Coventry University, Warwickshire NHS Trust**Coventry University, Warwickshire NHS Trust, and University Hospitals Coventry have joined forces with MOHAN Foundation to Advance Global Organ Donation and Transplantation**

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On October 16, 2024, a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) was signed between Coventry University and MOHAN Foundation. This strategic collaboration aims to run educational modules in organ donation and transplantation to make it available globally and further collaborative research.

The MoU exchange ceremony was held at Coventry University Group's India Hub in New Delhi with dignitaries such as Michael Houlgate (Deputy Director India at the British Council), Professor Nithya Krishnan (Consultant at University Hospitals Coventry and Warwickshire (UHCW) NHS Trust), Dr Sunil Shroff (Managing Trustee, MOHAN Foundation), Jonathan Young (Chief Medical Officer, University Hospitals Coventry and Warwickshire (UHCW) NHS Trust) and many others who attended online.

The chief guest, former MP Dr Vikas Mahatma, delivered keynote remarks and congratulated both the teams for this exciting project.

Experts Comments on Transplantation Tie-up

•Nithya Krishnan, Consultant Transplant Nephrologist at UHCW NHS Trust, was appointed as Professor of Clinical Health at Coventry University to lead on research and education links with India. She said, "These developments are very exciting, and we want to make training courses and materials on various aspects of organ donation and transplantation available for doctors and nurses globally. We also plan to advance research into the role of AI in improving transplant services. Our aim is to put UHCW NHS Trust and Coventry University on the world map of transplantation.

"Leena Kukreja, Regional Managing Director of Coventry University Group's India Hub, commented, "Coventry University Group is committed to benefiting the communities we serve, in the UK and internationally, and we look forward to sharing our research and teaching expertise to support this collaboration with MOHAN Foundation on organ transplantation. India's large and skilled talent pool, young population and thriving research sector make the country ideal for the Group's collaborative working approach, which saw the launch of the India Hub earlier this year to create long-term strategic partnerships with Indian Government, industry and higher education institutes.

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